

anides. The other bands attribute to bidentate perhenates^{1,18-15}.

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Synthesis of Indenyl and Fluorenyl Compounds of some Lanthanides

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THE only reported organolanthanide derivatives contain the cyclopentadienyl¹, indenyl^{2,3}, cyclooctatetraenyl⁴, and phenyl groups aside from the divalent compounds, $\text{Eu}(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5)_2$, $\text{Yb}(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5)_2$, $\text{Sm}(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5)_2$, $\text{OC}_4\text{H}_8(1)$ and $\text{Ln}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_8)_2$, where $\text{Ln} = \text{Eu}, \text{Yb}$, all these compounds involve the +3 oxidation state of the lanthanides. Although some attempts have been made to prepare alkyl and aryl derivatives⁵⁻⁷, no well characterised compound of this type have been prepared. Biphenyl was the only product isolated from both the sealed tube reaction of diphenyl mercury with metallic lanthanum at 135° for 100 h followed by treatment with carbon dioxide and of lanthanum trichloride with phenyl lithium in diethyl ether⁸. The present communication describes the preparation and

characterisation of triindenyl complexes of Sc, Y, Ce, Pr and Nd and trifluorenyl complexes of Sc, Y, La, Ce, Pr, Nd, Gd, Dy and Sm in +3 oxidation state.

Experimental

All operations were carried out under anhydrous conditions. Tetrahydrofuran was purified by distillation over Na and then over lithium hydride.

Potassium fluorenone and indenone: Potassium fluorenone and potassium indenone were prepared by treating potassium metal (1.17 g, 0.03 mol) with fluorene (5 g, 0.03 mol) and indene (3.5 g, 0.03 mol), respectively, in tetrahydrofuran with refluxing and stirring. Potassium reacted completely with indene to give dark brown coloured potassium indenone in 2 h, whereas with fluorene it gave an orange coloured solution of potassium fluorenone in 2.5 h.

Triindenyl lanthanides derivatives: Triindenyl complexes of Sc, Y, Ce, Pr and Nd were prepared by treating the corresponding anhydrous trichloride (1 mol) with potassium indenone (3 mol) in tetrahydrofuran. The reaction mixture was stirred for 8 h at room temperature followed by gentle reflux for 1-2 h to ensure complete reaction. The reaction mixture was filtered through G-4 sintered glass disc. Bulk of THF was distilled off under reduced pressure and the compounds were precipitated by adding petroleum ether (b.p. 40-60°). The precipitate was filtered through a G-4 sintered glass frit and dried under reduced pressure.

Microanalytical data of these complexes are given in Table I.

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF TRIINDENYL AND TRIFLUORENYL COMPLEXES OF LANTHANIDES

Compd.	Colour	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		
		C	H	Lanth.
$(\text{C}_9\text{H}_7)_2\text{Sc}$	Scarlet	82.72 (83.08)	5.04 (5.99)	10.90 (11.53)
$(\text{C}_9\text{H}_7)_2\text{Y}$	Light brown	74.13 (74.67)	4.52 (4.84)	19.80 (20.49)
$(\text{C}_9\text{H}_7)_2\text{Ce}$	Violet	65.90 (66.79)	3.87 (4.33)	28.00 (28.88)
$(\text{C}_9\text{H}_7)_2\text{Pr}$	Yellow	66.00 (66.68)	3.90 (4.32)	28.16 (29.00)
$(\text{C}_9\text{H}_7)_2\text{Nd}$	Dark brown	65.18 (66.23)	3.88 (4.30)	28.82 (29.47)
$(\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_9)_2\text{Sc}$	Brown	85.80 (86.67)	4.80 (5.0)	7.52 (8.33)
$(\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_9)_2\text{Y}$	Colourless	79.42 (80.15)	4.31 (4.62)	14.01 (15.28)
$(\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_9)_2\text{La}$	Light yellow	73.02 (73.83)	4.00 (4.26)	20.30 (21.91)
$(\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_9)_2\text{Ce}$	Pale yellow	73.11 (73.69)	3.96 (4.25)	21.50 (22.06)
$(\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_9)_2\text{Pr}$	Green	72.94 (73.59)	3.98 (4.25)	21.48 (22.16)
$(\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_9)_2\text{Nd}$	Yellow	72.04 (73.21)	3.90 (4.22)	21.90 (22.57)
$(\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_9)_2\text{Gd}$	Colourless	71.20 (71.75)	3.74 (4.14)	22.87 (24.11)
$(\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_9)_2\text{Dy}$	Colourless	70.69 (71.18)	3.76 (4.10)	23.30 (24.72)
$(\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_9)_2\text{Sm}$	Yellow	71.90 (72.52)	3.90 (4.18)	22.00 (22.30)

Trifluorenyl lanthanides: Anhydrous trichloride (1 mol) of Sc, Y, La, Ce, Pr, Nd, Gd, Dy and Sm were treated with potassium fluorenyl (3 mol) in THF. The other operations were similar as described in case of indenyl complexes. Lanthanides, carbon and hydrogen were estimated by standard methods (Table 1). Infrared spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer Infracord 137 spectrophotometer.

Results and Discussion

The preparation of the triindenyl and trifluorenyl complexes of lanthanides could be represented by the following equations,

where, Ln = lanthanide ion and R = indenyl (C_9H_7) or fluorenyl (C_{13}H_9) group. The compounds were stable in dry and inert atmosphere and usually decomposed on heating. These were soluble in polar solvents like acetone tetrahydrofuran and alcohols but insoluble in non-polar solvents like benzene, xylene, toluene and carbontetrachloride.

Infrared spectra:

Indenyl group: The presence of indenyl group in the triindenyl complexes of Sc, Y, Ce, Pr and Nd has been inferred from the presence of ir bands both due to cyclopentadienyl as well as phenyl groups. $\nu_{\text{C-H}}$, $\nu_{\text{C-C}}$ and C—H out-of-plane bending bands were observed at 3100–2900, 1460 and 820 cm^{-1} , respectively. The 1140 and 1020 cm^{-1} bands were due to deformation vibrations of ring protons⁵. In addition, the peaks at 1380 (C—H stretching), 1700–1750 (C—C stretching) and 750 cm^{-1} (C—H out-of-plane bending vibrations) are due to phenyl group in indene. The band at 720 cm^{-1} was due to methylene rocking vibration. Indene itself absorbs at 700 cm^{-1} ⁶.

Fluorenyl group: The ir spectra of trifluorenyl lanthanides (Sc, Y, La, Ce, Pr, Nd, Sm, Gd and Dy) are strikingly similar to the spectra of fluorene except for the absence or lowering in the intensities of the peaks associated with the methylene group at 2930, 1400, 1298, 1190, 950, 867, 853 cm^{-1} ⁶, whereas other peaks could be assigned as follows: 3100 and 2930 (C—H stretching), 1750–1550 (C—C stretching), 1000 cm^{-1} (C—H in-plane bending) and 750 cm^{-1} (C—H out-of-plane bending). The peak at 700 cm^{-1} may be due to the methylene rocking vibration (fluorene itself absorbs at 692 cm^{-1})⁶.

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Kinetics and Mechanism of the Complexation of Nickel(II) with DL-2-Aminobutanedicarboxylic Acid

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EARLIER investigations¹⁻⁴ deal with complexation of Ni^{II} with DL-2-aminobutanedicarboxylic acid only at 25°. In the present investigation, it is found that $k_1=0$ at 25° and increased with the increase in temperature, as reported by Cassatt and Wilkins¹. Complexation of Ni^{II} with DL-2-aminobutanedicarboxylic acid was investigated in the pH range 6.25–7.41, at 25–40 ($\pm 0.05^\circ$) and at ionic strength 0.3M NaNO_3 .

Experimental

DL-2-Aminobutanedicarboxylic acid (B.D.H.), 2,6-lutidine (Merck-Schuchardt), NaNO_3 and bromothymol blue (AnalaR) were used. Solution of Ni^{II} ($\sim 10^{-5}M$) was prepared from $\text{Ni}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Merck). Double-distilled water was used in the preparation of all solutions. Ionic strength of all reaction mixtures was adjusted to 0.3M (NaNO_3). Freshly prepared solution of DL-2-aminobutanedicarboxylic acid ($1.21 \times 10^{-3}M$) was used. A Radiometer pHM 26 pH meter was used for pH measurements.

Kinetic study was made using Aminco Morrow stopped flow spectrophotometer. The driving syringes and reaction chamber were thermostated at the desired temperatures with a circulating type Prufgerat NBE thermostat. Bromothymol blue ($\sim 10^{-5}M$) was added to DL-2-aminobutanedicarboxylic acid solution. Both metal and ligand were buffered with 0.05M 2,6-lutidine and the initial pH of the solutions containing metal and ligand were kept constant. Slight change in the pH (of the order of 0.05) was observed after mixing and the reported values are those of the reaction mixtures.

All the reactions were followed spectrophotometrically at 620 nm to monitor the change in absorbance with time. For every set, 10–15 runs were made and pseudo-first order rate constants were calculated from the plot of $\log \Delta V$ vs time.